

Bridging the Gap between Architectural Education and Architectural Practice

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Abstract:- Many freshly minted architects find, to their dismay, that there is a vast disparity between what we learn and what we really produce in the contemporary world, despite the fact that Architecture Education is a major contributor to the growth of the industry as a whole. This is a major problem. Despite the abundant "cut and paste" options available in the digital world, the prescribed systems and subject areas are now being taught very superficially and in isolation, and the prevailing teaching strategies for architecture are "Design Centric," ones that create "elevations," "3D views," and "walkthroughs." While it is now common knowledge that the world's greatest buildings were all "hand-made," the phrase "skills of hand" has gone into overuse. However, this research seeks to close a knowledge gap by illuminating the obstacles in architecture education that reduce graduates' marketability and offering solutions to these problems. Former architecture students, current and former faculty members, and working architects were each given one of four surveys to fill out and return. The research shows that several strategies have the potential to close the gap between architectural education and practice. These include moving towards more practical teaching methods, forming non-governmental organisations, merging architectural schools and practices, and revising the undergraduate architectural curriculum.

Keywords:- Architectural Education, Architectural Practice, Graduates, Architect and Nigeria

I. INTRODUCTION

An excellent example of the degree to which civilization is continually regulated and organized may be seen in its buildings. Working together effectively is a sign of seriousness and civic duty in this field. Although the goal of education is to provide students with the information, abilities, attitudes, and experiences they will need to succeed in life, the field of architecture is experiencing a shift in practice due to changes in architectural education. Educators examine teaching methods from a number of different angles. The concept of "job-oriented" education has been studied by a plethora of academics. Education that focuses on preparing students for the workforce is called "job-oriented" (Fami et al., 2010).

As architecture encompasses so many fields, there are many ways to approach it, each with its unique history that traces back to the humanities and the future. Each qualitative study offers a fresh point of view to the community as a

whole, altering the way in which current and future architecture are influenced by their predecessors. It is essential that research be integrated into practice, and that practice be supported by research. Due to the increased perceptiveness and digitalization of today's classrooms, engaging brainstorming sessions are essential to Architecture Education.

In Nigeria, there is not a unified approach to the education of architects. The degree to which colleges and universities focus on providing students with practical skills or academic knowledge varies widely. In some, one's occupation is the focus of one's life. Nonetheless, there may be conflicts between these stances in the context of professional architecture and the employment market (Mahdavinejad et al., 2012). According to data collected over two decades of graduate study in Architectural Science in Nigeria, The system's graduates have not been able to effectively enter the job market. The job market is robust for those with architectural training. Thus, problem-solving education should be a required element of the curriculum in every nation. To that end, this article first discusses the disconnect between architectural schools and the industry. Then, strategies for getting over their fundamental differences and coexisting together.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Holistic and All-Inclusive Methods in Architecture Training

Pre-design activities

Everybody from each enterprise to multinational conglomerates may count themselves among our satisfied customers. Each client has their own unique priorities in mind. And indeed, the amount of preparation that each client puts into a building project differs substantially (Rifaat, 2019). Many customers come to the architect with a clear idea of the kind of building they desire, whether it a home, a commercial/residential hybrid, an office building, a factory, or some other type of institution. A committee of people would have determined on the project's viability, site, and construction budget. However, many customers continue to go up unprepared, so architects must be ready to aid them (Rifaat, 2019).

The architect and other specialists will be required at different stages of the design process for every project, no matter how large or little. Any building projects would be unable to go forward without them. If any of these pre-design steps are neglected, significant problems may arise that would make further design work pointless or impossible (Fischer et al., 2017).

➤ *Budget and programme definition*

It is uncommon for clients to hire architects without a clear idea of what they want to achieve or how much money they have to work with. While an architect's involvement may be minimal in the case of a private residence, they may play a crucial role in the case of a large speculative development project by preparing schematic designs, consulting with real estate agents for market research, and estimating construction costs, often with the help of qualified building contractors.

➤ *Site selection*

Those who are in the market for an architect's services often either already have a particular piece of property in mind or have firm intentions to do so. The architect's input in such a situation would be crucial. The architect would next utilize their local expertise and/or advice from a real estate agent to narrow down the list of possible sites. Building regulations must be researched to see whether they allow for the construction of a project of the proposed size and scope. When you weigh your options, think about doing the following site assessments.

➤ *Site investigations*

The architect must regularly visit the site to inspect it in person and make notes on its condition and the surrounding surroundings. All projects also need attention to the following activities and fields of research.

➤ *Land Surveying*

There may have been an earlier survey of the site selected for the project. If the property owner does not have a surveyor on staff, the architect will assist in finding one. The property's location, adjoining roads, perimeter dimensions and orientation with respect to North, required building setbacks from property lines, existing below-grade utilities, etc., should all be accurately depicted on the survey, as should any easements or restrictions that may limit the property's use, such as when the site or portions thereof are subject to flooding. If there are current structures on the land, the survey will detail their positions and dimensions.

➤ *Geotechnical investigation*

Geotechnical research involves drilling boreholes and analyzing the core samples to learn about the soil's composition and bearing capacity. A structural engineer receives and inserts the information into the building's blueprints. Sometimes, all you need is the information from a single borehole to provide the foundation for an expedition. A further in-depth investigation is often the structural engineer's responsibility on larger projects and at more distant locations. The structural engineer would

specify how deep boreholes need to be dug to reach bedrock and gather information on the soil's properties, for instance, in extremely tall buildings.

➤ *Identifying and addressing environmental hazards*

This is possible that the planned project location had previously allowed activities that would have resulted in chemical soil pollution. Site inspections known as "Environmental One" and "Environmental Two" are mandated in such cases by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) Regulations. When the first type displays extreme contamination conditions, the second, more stringent type must be executed. Professional consultants perform the inspections, and licensed technicians remove and dispose of any hazardous substances found during the cleaning.

➤ *Establishing the availability of utilities infrastructure*

During the pre-design phase, it is common practice to bring in experts in several fields to evaluate the viability of the existing utility infrastructure and offer estimates of the project's utility needs. Information about utilities such as water, storm water, sanitary sewage, and electrical power cables is usually readily accessible online. Professionals would undertake a feasibility assessment to ascertain whether or not the project is financially viable and how much it would cost to connect utilities to the location of the project. It's also conceivable that there are already utility lines running through the area, which would need to be redirected. Engineers on the project would reassess the options and expenses involved. Several factors influence the likelihood of a project becoming profitable.

➤ *Identifying and protecting the best features of a certain area*

The architect has the option of keeping some of the site's preexisting buildings. A landscape architect may be required to evaluate the current state of a site and make decisions on the retention of natural features such as trees and cliff faces. The placement of various parts of the project is contingent on these factors.

➤ *Who accomplishes what throughout the preparatory, constructional, and final phases?*

The typical lifecycle of a construction project includes conceptual design, design development, construction document preparation, competitive bidding, building contractor selection, construction, and administration. Client/owner, architect, government, interdisciplinary team, several material, equipment, and system suppliers, and contractors are all players. "Figure 1" details the key players involved in each phase of the design and construction process.

Fig. 1: Illustrating the numerous phases involved in a construction phase in which the different entities and disciplines involved interact with one another.

The following is a summary of the key participants and what they brought to the table throughout the planning and construction phases.

➤ *The owner's role*

The design and construction processes are started by the owner. They start getting involved early on and continue to do so all the way through. The architect is relied on for advice throughout the project, especially when the stakes are high and decisions must be made quickly. They also foot the bill for building it and compensate the architect and design team.

➤ *The architect's role*

The architect is legally responsible for all aspects of the building process. After determining which fields and organisations need to be included in the project, the architect is responsible for creating a team of specialists to function under their supervision for the whole of the building process. During the design phase, they produce the necessary design drawings and share them with the rest of the team. The architect's job is to ensure that everyone involved in the building process is on the same page. Keep in mind that the architect should be copied on all official communication between the owner and the design and construction teams, since they are the project's principal point of contact. The duties of the architect at each stage of construction are outlined.

B. Schematic design

Schematic design is the initial effort by the architect to imagine a spatial solution for organizing a particular programme of applications in a logical way, and it marks the beginning of the design process. It is common practice in schematic design to brainstorm potential ideas, create presentation materials, consult with the customer to learn his preferences, and make necessary adjustments until he is satisfied. That is right; it is a lot like an architecture school

design studio, but the professor is replaced with the customer, whose opinions and demands carry more weight.

C. Design development

Much time and effort is spent throughout the design phase deliberating about which features should serve as the project's backbone. The architect and his specialized team work with many different manufacturers and construction product manufacturers and distributors whose wares may be used in the project's construction.

D. The preparation of Construction Documents

Because of the weight of these documents, we have capitalized their titles. They are designed to be comprehensive, covering every aspect of a construction project to ensure its timely and successful conclusion. The quantity and kind of needed documentation is directly proportional to the project's scope and complexity. As with the rest of the project, the Construction Documents are developed via teamwork overseen by the architect.

The Construction Papers provide blueprints and detailed instructions for building. The drawings cover the whole gamut of architectural specializations, from site plans and floor plans to elevations and sections to wall sections and details. Specifications are written descriptions of the building's materials and methods that kick off the construction phase. On drawings, specifications for smaller projects are sometimes merely sketched down in vague terms. Larger projects need individual, in-depth specification documents. Construction Documents (CDs) are submitted to the appropriate agencies together with a Building Permit application. After receiving feedback from the appropriate authorities, the papers must be amended and resubmitted for further consideration. After all necessary approvals have been granted by the appropriate authorities, a Building Permit may be issued, marking the end of the project's design phase.

E. Bidding and selection of building contractors

The building process may be approached from several perspectives. If the owner is also the contractor, he may get a building permit and start immediately. It's possible that the architect is also willing to operate as the project manager, managing the subcontractors and taking full responsibility for the final result. The architect and/or the owner may choose to collaborate with a predetermined builder. The following is a typical arrangement for awarding building contracts.

The Construction Contract Award will be worked out between the Architect and the Owner. It is common practice for the architect and the building owner to collaborate in the selection of general contractors and the subsequent distribution of bid requests. To use open bidding to choose a general contractor, bid requests must be published through appropriate media. Any potential buyers or investors will always have access to a complete set of Construction Documents. Overall financial strength and other factors are used to rank the submitted plans. Typically, the construction contract goes to the lowest bidder. It is important to remember that in most cases, the contractor would not have been foreseen or included in the planning stages of the project. However as shown in "Table 1," it is best to get in touch with construction companies early in the design process for cost estimates and advice based on their expertise working on projects similar to this one.

F. Construction

The architect will pay regular visits to the building site to make sure that everything is going according to plan. They pinpoint problem areas, record GPS coordinates, and send repair orders to the service provider. They review the contractor's technical shop drawings and financial files, as well as any changes required by the owner and the contractor, before making recommendations to the owner. When construction is finished, the architect must ensure that the owner pays all contractors in full, liens are removed, inspections are passed, a Certificate of Occupancy is issued, and the building is ready for occupancy.

➤ *Involvement of law enforcement and administrative agencies*

During the whole design and construction process, rules and regulations have an impact on professional design by a variety of disciplines. Several aspects of the preliminary design process are directly influenced by these regulations, including the maximum allowable floor area and height of the proposed building, the number and kind of parking spots required onsite, the location of exits, and the requirements of individuals with disabilities. Codes influence choices during design development and the compilation of construction documentation in a variety of ways, including the requirements for firefighting systems and equipment and the fire resistance ratings of structural systems and building components. Moreover, before a permit can be given, building paperwork must be reviewed, debated, and, in many cases, modified by the relevant authorities. Several different types of contractors are vetted and approved by the government to work on certain building projects. A

Certificate of Occupancy is issued after a final examination of a building, during which any outstanding issues are noted.

➤ *The Role of Consultants who are specialized*

The architect directs an interdisciplinary crew that performs all aspects of building.

➤ *Distributors and producers of building materials joining forces*

The entire number and variety of such sellers is unknown. They encompass everything from the foundation to the finishing touches, as shown by the fact that they incorporate renewable electrical power systems, elevators, and every conceivable kind of building material and finish. The information they provide is relied on heavily throughout the design process, from the first stages of brainstorming through the completion of construction documents. Participants in the construction process are those who have had their items selected. In light of the growing interest in sustainable building methods, suppliers of construction gear and supplies increasingly provide information on product recycling and the origins of their raw materials. This information is essential for life cycle evaluations and meeting sustainable development standards.

➤ *The role of building contractors*

Contractors are liable for carrying out their duties in accordance with the Construction Documents. In the conventional model, a general contractor (GC) oversees a team of subcontractors. The connection between an architectural firm and its professional sub-consultants is similar to that between a general contractor and its subcontractors. Subcontractors, like the various sub-consultants involved in a project, often specialise in a small set of duties.

A comprehensive construction schedule is developed by the general contractor and presented to the project's architect and owner for approval. They promise to keep the project on schedule by ensuring that all materials and equipment needed for construction arrive promptly and that all subcontractors show up for work on time. As a result, they are now the "conductor" of the construction operation.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The first step of this research was a descriptive-analytical analysis of Nigeria's architectural education system, with a focus on the gap between theory and practice. In this way, three groups of architects—freshmen, college and university faculty, and professional architects—have been evaluated. In order to achieve this goal, four different iterations of open-ended questions were created and evaluated. Three medium-sized universities provided participants for this study. We hand-picked each architect from the pool of available companies. The data quality was evaluated with the use of content analysis. Classifying and assessing content in relation to overarching themes and ideas is the goal of content analysis. Finally, a set of remedies has been proposed to close the gap between architectural education and the current architectural profession based on the findings from the first stage. To verify the veracity of the

suggestions given and to gauge how valuable they would be to the Department of Architecture, an open-ended questionnaire was developed and sent to the industry's top architects.

IV. FINDINGS

Based on the initial survey results, the following factors were identified as adding to the gap between architectural theory and practices.

A. *Inadequate competent work history and experience of lecturers and professors*

Applicants in modern-day Nigeria are judged not only on their grades but also on their abilities in science and research. Yet, lecturers and professors teaching the topic must be conversant with the whole process of planning and executing architectural projects in order to educate students on the real needs of the architectural sector. As a result, the selection process for architects has to evolve such that work experience is given the same weight as academic degrees.

B. *Missing link between the educational environment and society*

Only during a required three-month industrial training does the student interact with the outside world. Despite the importance of networks to the success of architects, the modern university has become a more isolated place to learn. Universities must, therefore, always have open-door policies. The students may then make use of the city's various resources, such as the many workshops, universities, architectural companies, community members, future jobs, etc.

C. *Not paying enough attention in architecture school*

Undergraduate architectural education does not appear to take the job market into account. As a consequence, the architectural education system has to change to accommodate the needs of the industry. The following subjects are underrepresented in architectural education:

➤ *Executive skills training:*

Although it is true that architects should be able to build, it is also clear that design has taken precedence in architectural education. But, given the current state of the architectural community, it is obvious that the most successful architects are the ones who can really construct their own designs. This means that the institution should provide as much as possible for student-designed projects' practical and workshop needs.

➤ *Adherence to rules and regulations:*

Architects are responsible for adhering to all rules and guidelines, including those established by governments and the technical community. Yet, these concerns have either been ignored or treated superficially in academic circles. Hence, students should take at least one design course as mandated by the actual laws and regulations of the town and the engineering organization.

➤ *Experiential skills acquisition:*

Successful architects must have strong interpersonal and communication skills. The university has been remiss in not modifying its policy to address this concern. Thus, the writers push for open-gated institutions and other forms of alternative education, including rituals, seminars, displays, etc.

➤ *Training in Ethics:*

According to the data, the importance of professional ethics in the eyes of architecture businesses is high. The institution, however, avoids confronting the issue directly. Thus, institutions of higher learning need to make an active effort to solve this issue.

➤ *Architectural software training:*

Graduates of architecture programmes must be well-versed in the use of architectural software. Despite the growing significance of architectural software, it is still only the subject of a single university-level degree. Because of this, many educational institutions now offer optional courses in architectural drawing software such as AutoCAD, 3D Max, Revit, Rhino, etc.

➤ *Training and Development in Business skills*

While the competition for jobs is high, learning business skills might be useful. The importance of being able to compete in the market has grown as the number of architectural firms around the country has increased. No one in the architectural department seemed interested.

D. *Failure to invest in the development of one's own traits:*

➤ *Students' lack of drive:*

The enthusiasm of architecture students to learn and improve has been steadily declining, according to teachers and professors.

➤ *Lack of perseverance of students*

Students who stick through the tough times are more likely to succeed in school and in their careers. Annual surveys of university faculty members reveal a decline in architecture students' steadfastness. The scope of architectural study requires students to have a great deal of patience.

➤ *Graduates' lack of confidence*

Self-assurance is a characteristic shared by those who excel in school and the workplace. Aspiring architects should have strong interpersonal skills.

➤ *Unfocused students*

One of the most crucial aspects of people's efforts and development is the use of objectives. By narrowing your attention to what matters most, you achieve your objectives. Many students of contemporary architecture, however, continue to chase the pitch without any clear destination in sight.

➤ *Poor Professional Prospects*

Like many other nations, Nigeria has a serious challenge with high unemployment rates. With the current economy situation and the high unemployment rate among recent architecture school graduates, the profession's future seems bleak and unclear. Students studying architecture are aware of this and no longer have lofty professional aspirations as a result.

E. Saturated architectural employment market due to the widespread turnover of architecture students

The abundance of recent architecture graduates has lowered professional standards and flooded the employment market. Competition for students is high among the various colleges and universities that welcome architecture majors with little or no requirements. Some construction workers lack a formal education in architecture but nonetheless contribute to the industry.

F. Short education time

In Nigeria, earning a bachelor's degree in architecture takes almost the same length of time as earning a bachelor's degree in any other branch of engineering: five years. Yet, it seems this time frame is inadequate to equip graduates to thrive in the work market since the area of architecture is so

vast. The standard amount of time needed to learn the ropes and become an architect is six years. It would imply that graduates of such programmes fared better in the job market than their younger contemporaries in the field of architecture.

Based on what was learned in the first stage, the following suggestions were made to help reduce the skills gap in the workplace (Table 1).

- Modifications to the selection criteria for the architectural faculty member, to take into account both academic qualifications and professional experience.
- Turning Architectural Universities into "Social Universities"
- Participatory training methods are used.
- Alterations to the Bachelor's Degree in Architecture.
- Connecting schools of architecture with design firms
- The establishment of advocacy groups like NGO's committed to spreading architectural knowledge among the general public
- Recruiting future architects using practical examination and personal interviews.
- Making use of the system of ongoing education.

Table 1:

S/N	Factors	Recommendations
1	Professors' inexperience and lack of expertise	Modifications to the faculty hiring process for Architects
2	Isolation of schools from the rest of society	Establishing nongovernmental organisations (NGOs) and converting architectural schools into "social schools"
3	Insufficient focus on architecture as a career in architectural schools	Participatory training methods are used.
	a) Executive skills training	Changes to the undergraduate architecture program.
	b) Adherence to rules and regulations:	Connecting universities' architecture programs with professional practices.
	c) Experiential skills acquisition	
	d) Training in Ethics	
	e) Architectural software training	
	f) Training and Development in Business skills	
4	Students of architecture are rarely taught how to cultivate their own personalities.	Changes to the undergraduate architecture program
	a) Students are not motivated	
	b) There is no tenacity from students	
	c) Graduates do not have confidence	
	d) Students have no set target to pursue	
	e) Not interested in a future career	
5	Massive influx of architecture graduates into a competitive employment market	Acceptance based on demonstrated competence and personal interviews
6	Limited time for learning	Continuous master's degree programmes

*** Recommendations for bridging the gap between theory and practice in architecture education.***

The second part of the study was administering a questionnaire to architects based on the proposed solutions so that they could assess the ideas' viability and potential applications inside architectural education institutions. The following is a summary of the outcomes.

➤ *Participatory education*

Experts agree that one of the most effective ways to teach architecture is via student participation. They suggest architectural schools implement ateliers for participatory education, where several instructors, students of varying ages, and a variety of classes are held simultaneously. Several of these sessions may also benefit from the participation of licensed architects. The ateliers at several institutions are an example of interactive education on a larger scale. In such a scenario, collegiate collaboration will strengthen. Yet, these ateliers facilitate communication amongst students. Lastly, participatory learning in the form of ateliers among architecture and related students might be seen as an overarching concept. The pluses of using this strategy are:

- When there are students of varied years present, the younger students might gain by the transactions made by the older, more knowledgeable students.
- The structure of courses makes it easier to grasp their interdependencies and find productive ways to combine their use.
- Seeing and speaking with working architects might help students develop some of the knowledge and abilities they'll need to get employment in the industry.
- Students from various backgrounds may be brought together by merging the systems of numerous institutions and making up for the deficiencies of each.
- Students of architecture may learn skills in other fields by taking advantage of the interdisciplinary nature of architecture studios.

➤ *Experts have proposed turning architecture schools into "social schools" in response to this enquiry; under this model, students, clients, and members of the general public are all welcome at universities that specialize in the built environment. Advantages of this approach include:*

- Clients may choose to communicate with architects directly if they so like.
- Academic art schools and professional architectural firms (ateliers) may communicate and work together on projects.
- The architectural school becomes more in tune with community needs after establishing a connection with the neighbourhood.

➤ *NGOs*

Some researchers claim that the gap can be filled without the involvement of non-governmental organisations since there are so many architecture schools and businesses. Most experts, however, agree that NGOs may help bridge the skills gap and can be used in a variety of contexts. Methods like this include the ones listed below:

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schools and businesses. Most experts, however, agree that NGOs may help bridge the skills gap and can be used in a variety of contexts. Methods like this include the ones listed below:

- Creating an individualized architectural foundation for high school graduates to take into college. 3. These organisations are crucial for new architecture graduates entering the industry because they provide an environment where students, recent graduates, instructors, professionals in the field of architecture, as well as customers from the private, public, and non-profit sectors. So, you may attract not just students but also corporations, student organisations, and maybe even your first serious professional project.

➤ *Bringing together architectural institutes and firms:*

To establish this link in the first case, the undergraduate architecture curriculum would need to be revised to include a minimum of two semesters of internship in a university-approved and -supervised architectural firm. The student will complete their degree after participating in this curriculum, which is very much like an apprenticeship. Advantages of this approach include:

- The student is given an overview of architecture and urged to put in the necessary work to become a professional architect.
- As architecture is really about making things, theoretical training alone is insufficient. This allows for students to get training in a realistic setting.
- Students might begin building their professional networks as undergraduates. Under the alternative scenario, universities have the power to establish architectural offices. The School Renovation Organization and local governments provide examples of public and private clients that educational institutions may work with to provide their students hands-on experience with real-world academic projects. Advantages of this approach include:
 - ✓ Generating funding for the university through architectural projects
 - ✓ Training students with real projects
 - ✓ Reducing costs for clients who go to the university architecture offices

➤ *Adding additional courses (1. Executive Skills Training, 2. Education of Rules and Regulations, 3. Interactive Skills Training, 4. Professional Ethics Training 5. Architectural Software Training, 6. Business Skills Training) to the undergraduate architecture curriculum:*

The problem, is not in the inclusion of classes on executive concerns (such as "Building Courses 1 and 2," "Technical Design," etc.), but in the instruction of the lecturer-professor and the selection of subjects. Yet, the quality of these classes suffers since they are not delivered in building workshops, where they would be most effective.

The unit on architectural software is also included in the curriculum, but it receives little attention and the vast majority of architecture lecturers and professors are not experts in the programme themselves. They claim that the additional courses should be required but that implementing

them would require a complete overhaul of the undergraduate curriculum.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations aim to bridge the disparity between professional and academic architecture by addressing the issues in architecture education that have led to the current state of the architectural profession.

- The implementation of student participation in courses: the case of participatory architecture ateliers course combinations and cross-year instruction are taken into account. These ateliers have many instructors and a wide range of students from various classes and years. At these workshops, licenced architects are welcome to participate in meetings as observers. The architecture ateliers of many colleges and fields may be brought together for a more all-encompassing study of participatory architectural education.
- Transforming architectural schools into social schools: Schools of architecture must be changed into community schools in order to open their doors to the public and allow for the presence of community members as well as students, lecturers and professors, customers, professionals, etc. in the university setting.
- Establishment of NGOs: Putting in place non-governmental organisations to serve as a bridge between design studios, employers, and customers. The involvement of non-governmental organisations (NGOs) is crucial in linking architectural education with its professional employment. NGOs spring out from the very centre of society. Thus, it only makes sense that architectural programmes actively include the public. Thus, it is advised that architectural schools form groups like trade unions to serve as intermediaries between students and the local community. There are several ways in which the architectural community may benefit from these groups:
 - ✓ Community Awareness: The difficulty of comprehending the architectural community is one of the field's major issues. That is, the general public has no perspective on what architects do or how it can affect them, and often dismisses architects' work as a matter of taste and a pointless source of contention. Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) may lead the charge in educating the general public about architecture.
 - ✓ Developing an individual perspective on architecture for incoming freshman students.
 - ✓ Assisting those new to the workforce in the field of architecture, these groups may arrange for the coexistence of students, recent graduates, teachers, practising professionals, and even private, public, and non-governmental organisations.
- Connecting schools of architecture with professional architectural practice: To make this connection, undergraduate architectural education must be rethought as a whole. So that they may spend a few semesters working under supervision in an authorised architectural firm. They proceed to the final semesters when they have acquired and honed the requisite abilities. Moreover, universities have the legal right to establish architecture departments. Colleges and colleges may equip students for

the workforce by taking on real-world projects from organisations like the School Renovation Organization and local governments.

- Undergraduate architecture curriculum revision: One of the most evident demands of the architectural sector is a change of the undergraduate curriculum to reflect the realities of the profession's labour market. Due of the extensive research required for curriculum modification, this study has focused only on identifying the gaps in the architectural education system. The names of these classes are:
 - ✓ Executive skills training
 - ✓ Adherence to rules and regulations:
 - ✓ Experiential skills acquisition
 - ✓ Training in Ethics
 - ✓ Architectural software training
 - ✓ Training and Development in Business skills.

In addition to the above:

- The current procedure for selecting new department members in the field of architecture must be revised to take into consideration a candidate's practical experience in addition to his or her academic credentials.
- The admissions process for an architectural programme should include both a practical test and an interview.
- The current system of Master's degrees should be utilised to extend the time spent in university education.

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